

MODERN TEACHING METHODS USED IN TEACHING ECONOMICS AT THE INSTITUTE

KHUDOYNAZAR ERGASHEV¹, MAKSUD KHUSANOV² and TOLIB KHOLIKOV³

¹Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, Uzbekistan.

^{2,3}Assistant Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, Uzbekistan.

Email: ¹Ergashev1962@mail.ru, ²xusanov.makhsud84@gmail.com, ³Xoliqov0220@mail.ru

Abstract

The use of various teaching methods makes it possible to make lessons in economics interesting, accessible for understanding by different age groups of students. Active teaching methods allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, to understand real economic situations. Heuristic teaching methods enable students to show their creativity, look for non-standard solutions to various economic problems. The use of various teaching methods, combining them makes it possible to achieve the best result in teaching the economy to students, obtaining them versatile knowledge on the subject, developing creative thinking, the ability to set tasks and solve them. The purpose of the article is the modern teaching methods used in teaching economics to study the organizational and methodological process of teaching economics in institutes.

Keywords: Dialogue, Debate, Discussion, Brainstorming, Group Work, Business Games, Empirical Experience, Exchange of Information, Experience, Control

INTRODUCTION

The teaching method is a way of interconnected activity of the teacher and students to achieve the goals of teaching, development and education. The choice of teaching methods depends on many circumstances and conditions for the course of the educational process, the nature and content of the subject, specifically on:

1. The level of knowledge and skills of the teacher. The teacher needs to know and understand the essence of the method, the classification of teaching methods, the basis of a particular type of classification, be able to apply them in various situations and combinations. Using this or that system of methods, diverse or complementary, focused on achieving a common goal, the teacher establishes feedback with students, reveals the level of assimilation of knowledge and skills, determines the effectiveness of the application of methods and makes adjustments, thereby increasing their level of professional competence.
2. The general goal and objectives of learning, the characteristics of the subject, topic, planned goals and objectives of a particular lesson.
3. The content of the educational material selected by the teacher.
4. The level of development of students, their ability to learn, opportunities and age characteristics.
5. The role of a method or a combination of methods in the development of students' cognitive activity, their activity, independence and creativity.
6. Time.

The methods used in economics lessons can be divided into the following groups:

- Methods of one-sided presentation of educational material (teaching): story, explanation, lecture.
- Methods of two-sided presentation of material: dialogue, debate, discussion, brainstorming, group work, business games;
- Methods for covering empirical experience (exchange of information, experience, etc.);
- Methods of various types of training: problem-based, heuristic, student-centered, etc.;
- Methods of control and feedback (conversation, consultation, testing, test, exam, etc.).

When organizing classes in economics at institute, it is important to use active teaching methods, because they allow students to understand the practical significance of the economy, apply theoretical knowledge in this discipline in practice, understand the structure and mechanism of the functioning of some enterprises, etc.

According to the degree of activation of students and the nature of their educational and cognitive activity, they differ: simulation methods based on pedagogical techniques and special forms of conducting classes, in which educational, cognitive and research activities are built on imitation of future professional and practical activities and non-imitation methods that are built on real professional and practical situations.

METHODOLOGY

As part of an institute course in economics, it is advisable to use such a type of active learning as business games. They contribute to the formation of not only professional, but also job knowledge, skills and abilities. The business game is a model substitution of two realities - production processes and processes of people's activity in it.

The methodological support of the business game should include:

- 1) initial information about the business game;
- 2) methodology for preparing and conducting a business game;
- 3) a set of various forms and other documentation.

Classroom classes at institute in teaching economics play a dominant role, because independent study of this science is quite difficult for students. The main type of classroom activity is the lesson. This is a form of organizing the activities of a permanent staff of teachers and students in a certain period of time, systematically used to solve the problems of teaching, educating and developing students.

Currently, there are several criteria by which types of lessons can be classified:

1. Depending on the various psychological and pedagogical stages of mastering the material by students:

- Lessons of learning new material;
- Lessons to consolidate knowledge, skills and abilities;
- Iterative-generalizing lessons;
- Lesson of control, evaluation and correction of students' knowledge;

Combined lessons.

2. Depending on the teaching methods used in the lesson:

- Lessons - lectures;
- Lessons - seminars;
- Lessons - workshops.

Therefore, when studying this training course, it is necessary to take into account these features, organize different types of lessons in different ways. A lesson in learning new material can take place in various forms: lectures, workshops, games. The purpose of this type of lesson is the study and primary awareness of new educational material by students, understanding the connections and relationships in the objects of study. The main time is devoted to the transfer and assimilation of new knowledge, skills and abilities. In the lesson, various methods of activating the activity of students are used: giving the material presented a problematic character, including various examples in the material being studied, including real examples from the surrounding reality, involving students in an active discussion of the questions posed by the teacher. The teacher activates the attention and mental activity of students, systematizes the knowledge they have received.

The structure of the lesson for studying new material in economics:

1. Organizational beginning, introduction to the lesson (preparation for the assimilation of new material, linking concepts already covered in previous lessons with new material);
2. Setting goals and objectives of the lesson;
3. Presentation and explanation of the new material, including both the teacher's explanation and the self-acquaintance of students with the material (involving students in a conversation about the problems under consideration, working with reference literature, etc.);
4. Performing practical work by students to consolidate new material (setting tasks for work in small groups, discussing examples given by the teacher, using active and gaming teaching methods);
5. Sounding homework and comments to it;
6. Summing up the lesson, answering students' questions on the topic of the lesson.

When conducting a lesson on learning new material, the teacher should take into account the following recommendations: it is necessary to motivate students to memorize new material, work with various materials that contribute to the development of memory in students. Also, for the best assimilation of the material covered, it is necessary to constantly apply the knowledge and skills acquired by the student in the past to assimilate new material.

The next type of lesson is the lesson of consolidating new knowledge, skills and abilities. Usually these types of lessons are held immediately after learning new material. The purpose of such a lesson is the secondary comprehension of already known knowledge, the development of skills and abilities for their application. The tasks of lessons of this type are aimed at developing and shaping skills and abilities in the process of educational and practical activities.

Starting a lesson of this type, the teacher, first of all, must determine whether the students have understood the previously studied material correctly enough, to what extent they have mastered it, what difficulties students have when operating with theoretical knowledge in the course of performing practical actions.

If it turns out that individual facts of a theoretical nature are not deeply understood by students, care must be taken to ensure that during the implementation of practical exercises the discovered gap is eliminated by providing additional clarifications on this topic.

The structure of the lesson to consolidate new knowledge and skills:

1. Organization of the beginning of the lesson;
2. Setting goals and objectives of the lesson;
3. Practical tasks of various types and levels of complexity on the material studied, the inclusion of students in independent work under the guidance of a teacher (conducting business games, introducing a case method, discussing the problems of new material, listening and discussing abstracts and reports prepared by students);
4. Summarizing the work, showing the results achieved, collective discussion of concepts, terms, situations, clarifying any features, marking students, discussing mistakes made by students and correcting them;
5. generalization of the main ideas, provisions, hypotheses, conclusions, determination of the trends in the development of the topic in science and its connections with other topics of the training course in economics;
6. Statement of homework and commentary on its implementation.

This type of lesson is interesting in that it almost does not use the classical explanation of the material by the teacher. New information, explanations, individual reports are made by students directly in the course of the implementation of the planned work. Preparing for the lesson, the teacher selects the appropriate material and types of work, setting questions for the lesson.

Achieving the didactic goals of the lesson is also associated with the organization of the control and evaluation function. A variety of tasks and types of work suggests an optimal combination

of individual and general surveys based on problematic issues and situations with a transition to oral and written practical tasks.

Repetitive-generalizing lessons are usually held at the end of the study of a topic or a large section of the program. The purpose of the repetitive-generalizing lesson is the development by students of knowledge of the economy in the system, the generalization of single concepts into a system of knowledge about the subject. Didactic tasks of such lessons:

formation of a system of theoretical knowledge among students on the main topics or sections of the economy;

highlighting the key provisions studied in previous lessons, the relationship of the studied facts, events, the formation of concepts, the systematization of knowledge;

testing and recording knowledge, skills and abilities on the topics studied, sections, all educational material for various periods of time (quarter, half year, year).

The types of repetitive-generalizing lessons are a business game, a seminar, a conference, a round table. Repetitive-generalizing lessons should include a number of didactic components that are important differentiating features of lessons of this type: checking differentiated homework; in-depth work on theoretical information in connection with the understanding of the studied material at the level of broader generalizations; performance by students of differentiated practical tasks with a gradual increase in their level of complexity; control over the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities, which implies a high level of independent work of students.

The structure of the iterative-generalizing lesson:

1. Organization of the beginning of the lesson, setting its goals and objectives;
2. Direct repetition of educational material: the use of different types of survey: oral in the form of a presentation of the topic, frontal, interview, discussion; written - in the form of solving problems, analyzing economic situations, testing work on the topic. Checking homework aimed at repeating the basic concepts learned during previous lessons;
3. Summing up the results of the work with an analysis of the meaningfulness of the depth of knowledge, indicating the methods of independent work, determining the guidelines for working on new educational content;
4. Announcement of homework.

The lessons of generalization and systematization of knowledge form the need for constant repetition of educational material. They highlight the main theoretical provisions, generalize knowledge on various topics, establish interdisciplinary connections. Students learn to transfer the acquired experience to new conditions and situations.

The next type of lessons are the lessons of control and correction of knowledge and skills. Such lessons are used to determine and evaluate the quality of assimilation of theoretical knowledge, worldview and spiritual and moral values, a system of scientific concepts, ways of creative

activity. Evaluation of students' knowledge and skills shows their quality, reflects the degree of assimilation of the program material and the level of students' learning. The purpose of the lesson of control and correction of students' knowledge is to determine the level of mastery of knowledge by students.

The structure of this type of lesson:

1. The organizational beginning of the lesson, the psychological setting of students for composure, calmness, confidence, readiness for work;
2. Setting goals and objectives of the lesson, updating the role of control;
3. The main part of the lesson - instruction, issuance of tasks of the control type, direct independent work of students under the supervision of the teacher;
4. The final part - summarizing the work, analyzing typical errors and their causes, choosing rational solutions, preventing lagging and underachievement of some students, determining the general trend in the assimilation of program material, highlighting well-written works, commenting on them, orienting students to study the upcoming material. The control includes lessons on writing control, test papers, credit lessons. These lessons make it possible to identify a system of student attitudes to learning, to various aspects of educational activity, which contributes to the use of a student-centered approach to learning, making changes to the learning process and adjustments to the content and organization of learning.

A combined lesson is a type of lesson characterized by a combination (combination) of various goals and types of educational work during its implementation: knowledge testing, work on the material covered, presentation of new material, etc. The following stages are distinguished in the structure of the combined lesson:

- organization of students for classes;
- Repetitive training work on the material covered;
- work on understanding and assimilation of new material;
- work to consolidate the material presented;
- Work on the application of knowledge in practice and the formation of skills and abilities;
- setting homework.

The teacher may follow a different structure of the combined lesson. From Comenius and Herbart originates the classical four-link structure of the lesson, based on the formal steps (levels) of education: preparation for the assimilation of new knowledge; assimilation of new knowledge and skills; their consolidation and systematization; application in practice. The type of lesson corresponding to it is called combined (mixed). This type of lesson is called combined, because the teacher has the opportunity to achieve several goals. The elements (stages) of the lesson can be combined in any sequence, which makes the lesson flexible and

applicable to a very wide range of educational tasks. This, in particular, explains the widespread use of the combined lesson in mass practice; according to some data, the share of combined lessons is 75--80% of the total number of all lessons.

RESULTS

The viability of the classical combined lesson was also determined by the fact that it is better than other types in accordance with the laws of the educational process, the dynamics of mental performance and provides teachers with more opportunities to adapt to specific conditions. In addition to its important advantage - the ability to achieve several goals in one lesson, a combined lesson also has disadvantages. They are manifested in the fact that there is practically not enough time not only for the assimilation of new knowledge, but also for all other types of cognitive activity. Since the time when the combined lesson was proposed, there have been radical changes: the amount of knowledge studied in the lesson has increased significantly, classes are overcrowded in many institutes, which makes it difficult to manage cognitive processes, the attitude of students to learning has worsened, and therefore the productivity of all stages of the lesson has decreased. In order to increase the effectiveness of training sessions, other types of lessons have arisen and are being practiced, in which students are mainly engaged in any one type of activity. These are the lessons of assimilation of new knowledge; formation of new skills; generalization and systematization of knowledge, skills; control and correction of knowledge, skills; application of knowledge and skills in practice. All these types of lessons are included in the combined lesson. Thus, combined lessons can be developed by the teacher in accordance with the learning objectives of students, they are quite effective in teaching economics.

DISCUSSION

The classification of lessons, allocated according to the teaching methods used in them, includes lessons - lectures, lessons-seminars and practical lessons. A lecture is a systematic, consistent presentation of educational material, any issue, topic, section, subject, methods of science. The main requirements for the lesson - lectures are scientific, ideological, accessible, unity of form and content, emotional presentation, organic connection with other types of training sessions - seminars, laboratory work, educational and industrial practice, etc. Lectures are an organic part of the system of training sessions, they should be meaningfully linked to their complex, to the nature of the academic discipline, to the subject curriculum. A lecture on economics can be structured either as an inductive or deductive presentation of the material, or as a sequential consideration of independent issues of the program. The lecture must include an element of goal-setting and summing up. When organizing lessons - lectures on economics, the teacher must take into account various factors: firstly, he must be able to correctly calculate the time allotted for him to present the material, as well as the time to answer students' questions on the topic of the lesson. The teacher needs to be able to keep the attention of the audience to the topic of the lesson, use auxiliary material, give vivid examples that are interesting for students. At the end of the lesson, it is necessary to once again focus the attention of students on the main concepts explained during the lecture, indicate the relationship of the lecture topic

with other topics of the training course, explain homework, and answer students' questions.

Seminar - a form of educational and practical classes in which students discuss messages, reports and abstracts made by them based on the results of educational or scientific research under the guidance of a teacher.

Lessons - seminars are a kind of repetitive-generalizing lessons. Seminars allow you to deeply generalize the material studied, educate students in an active, creative attitude to educational work, and improve the skills of independent work. The teacher in conducting such lessons is the coordinator of discussions on the topic of the seminar. The purpose of the seminar is to form the skills of professional polemics and consolidate the material under discussion.

Seminars are usually held on specific issues related to the generalization of a number of theoretical issues and related practical skills. The methodology for preparing and conducting seminars on economics at institute is as follows: the teacher breaks down the general topic chosen for discussion at the seminar into 4-5 subtopics and compiles lists of references for the topic as a whole. Then the students are divided into small subgroups, each of which chooses one of the private subtopics to prepare a message (reports, abstracts). The teacher advises the students, helps them to choose the literature necessary for the answer, to draw up a plan. Then, for about a week, students collect working material for reports, write a plan for their future speech, and prepare presentations. It is necessary to ensure that each of the students, taking part in the collective development of the topic, prepares an individual presentation. To make a presentation on a particular subtopic, students are given no more than 5-7 minutes. At the end of the presentation, students answer questions from the teacher and their classmates. At the end of the lesson, the teacher is recommended to leave 7-10 minutes for a general summing up of the seminar, analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of students' work, and grading.

CONCLUSION

Lessons - workshops are the most important part of the lessons in economics at institute, because in these classes, economic problems are solved, the theoretical knowledge received by students is applied to resolve any issues of the economy. It is most advisable to conduct workshops when repeating and generalizing knowledge on previously studied material. Preparing for the lesson, students repeat the theoretical information necessary for the workshop in advance. In the classroom, various aids are usually used - reference books, technical tools, graphs, tables. The plan of the practical lesson should correspond to the general ideas and focus of the taught program of the course and correlate with it in the sequence of topics.

The structure of the practical lesson:

1. Entry of the teacher;
2. Practical part (solving problems, discussing economic situations, building tables and graphs);
3. Teacher's answers to questions on obscure material;
4. Statement of homework, the final word of the teacher.

At practical lessons, students can be asked to solve problems in various areas of the economy - pricing, taxation, management and accounting, budgeting, etc. Practical classes should be organized in such a way that students constantly feel the increase in the complexity of the tasks performed, experience positive emotions from experiencing their own success in learning, be busy with intense creative work, searching for correct and accurate solutions. Individual approach and productive pedagogical communication are of great importance. When developing tasks and a lesson plan, the teacher must take into account the level of preparation and interest of each student, acting as a consultant. Conducting lessons - workshops allows students to better understand theoretical issues, to realize the practical importance of the economy in the modern world. Practical exercises are designed to deepen, expand, and detail the knowledge gained in lectures in a generalized form, as well as to promote the development of professional skills. They develop scientific thinking and speech, allow students to test their knowledge and act as a means of prompt feedback.

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